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PREVALENCE OF COLOUR VISION DEFECT AND ITS RELATION WITH AMBLYOPIA AND REFRACTIVE ERROR IN SCHOOL GOING CHILDREN (6-16 YEARS)

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ABSTRACT: -

PURPOSE: - To determine the prevalence of colour vision defect and its correlation with amblyopia and refractive error in school going children.

Method: - In this population based prospective, cross-sectional study, 4057 children were examined from the random school selected from different areas of Bhuj, Ahmedabad, Modasa and Surendranagar from 6-16 years of age. A complete eye examination was conducted which includes detailed History, Visual acuity, Colour vision assessment, Refractive error measurement, Ocular deviation determination, Accommodation and Convergence and lastly Anterior and Posterior segments evaluation. Children who could not answer 4 or more plates correctly, then child was consider as colour vision deficient. Amblyopia was detected by taking pinhole visual acuity which was lesser than 0.4 in LogMAR. Ocular disease condition was assessed

Results: - Color vision deficiency (CVD) was detected in 20 children indicating a prevalence of 0.5 %. The prevalence of CVD in male children (0.6%) was higher compared to female children (0.4 %). The mean age of patient with CVD and without CVD was 12.23 and 12.6 whose p-value was 1.28 which indicates no significant difference in the age group of both the category. The mean V/A LogMAR of the children with CVD was normal compared to the children without CVD. There was no correlation of children of CVD with Refractive error, Amblyopia, Strabismus and Anisometropia.

Conclusion: - In our study we concluded that the colour blindness mostly affects boys but it can affect both the gender. Red and green deficiency is most common because of its genetic heritage. Along with it, there was no relationship between CVD and type of Amblyopia, Refractive error, Anisometropia or Strabismus.

Keywords: - Prevalence, Amblyopia, Refractive error, Color vision defect, School going children

Introduction

Human beings have the special ability to see in colour, which distinguishes them from other species. Colour vision is the ability to discriminate a light stimulus as a function of its wavelength. The Young Helmholtz theory of trichromatic colour vision, postulates the existence of three kinds of cones, each containing a different photo pigment which is maximally sensitive to one of the three primary colours. Normal, or trichromatic, colour vision is mediated by three types of cone photoreceptors – designated short- (S), middle- (M), and long- (L) wavelength-sensitive, showing peak absorbencies at light wavelengths of 415 nm, 530 nm and 560 nm, respectively. Blue, green and red are thus called primary colours as any colour can be produced by mixing appropriate proportion of these three colours.

Colour vision deficiency (CVD) or dyschromatopsia is the inability to distinguish certain colours. Molecular studies have shown that defects in colour vision result from the absence,

malfunction, or alteration of one (dichromatism), two (monochromatism) or all (achromatism) of the photopigments. Dichromats base their colour vision on only two pigments. The class of dichromats characterized by the entire absence of blue, green and red are called tritanopia, deuteranopia and protanopia respectively while those characterized by a relatively mild form of defective colour vision for blue, green and red are called as tritanomaly, deuteranomaly and protanomaly respectively. ^[1]

One of the most common forms of inherited color vision deficiency is the red–green deficiency or deuteranopia. This type of color blindness is passed on via the X chromosome and is more common in men who have only the one X chromosome, than in women, who have two X chromosomes. In men, the prevalence of color blindness is around 5.0% to 8.0%, while in women the prevalence is only 0.5% to 1.0%.

Since female offspring always receive one X chromosome from their mother and one from their father, a color-blind father always transmits the gene for color blindness to any daughters he may have. These daughters then become carriers of the gene and have a 50% chance of passing the abnormal gene to their sons. A color-blind man cannot transmit the condition to his male offspring, since the male always inherits the mother's X chromosome. ^[2]

Studies have also reported about the prevalence and mechanism of CVD among patients with myopia, amblyopia, media opacities, macular or retinal abnormalities, and optic nerve disorders. The colour spectrum is perceived by different color wavelength sensitive cones which also have an effect on control of accommodation and refractive error, therefore problems with color perception may impact accommodation and refractive errors. ^[3]

Colour Blindness has an enormous personal, social and economic impact limiting the education and life choices of otherwise healthy people & placing a significant weight on family, community, social & health service. Group of diseases and conditions occurring in childhood or early adolescence, which, if left untreated leads to severe visual impairment that are likely to be untreatable later in life (blindness). As we all know one of the most important organs in the human body are eyes and the most wonderful gift is vision, the importance of eye is neglected by many people by not paying proper attention towards eye care.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), about 75% of causes of blindness can be avoided through preventive or therapeutic measures. Control of childhood blindness is main priority of the WHO through its programme "VISION 2020: the Right to Sight". In the developing countries 25% of the populations are constituted by children in the school-going age group (6-15 years). They fall best in the preventable blindness age group & schools are the best for imparting health education to the children. Children do not complain of defective vision, may not even be aware of their problem. Children make various adjustments to the poor eyesight by sitting near the blackboard, holding the books closer to their eyes, squeezing the eyes, avoiding work requiring visual concentration. Schools are also one of the best centers for effectively implementing the comprehensive eye healthcare programme. ^[4]

So as soon as possible one can detect the colour vision deficiency, it become easy for the person to choose the career and make some of its changes in their life style. So the aim of this study is to find the CVD in school going children and its correlation with amblyopia and refractive error. Along with it, provide the guidelines to the school teachers and parents about the CVD.

Methods

In this population based cross-sectional randomized study, out of the various suburban school of Ahmedabad, Modasa, Surenderanagar and Bhuj including public and private schools, the schools were randomly selected whom the school screening camp was offered to Porecha Eye Hospital, Bareja. The time duration was from July 2022 to January 2024. Total 4057 students

of 18 schools were included in this study out of which 2137 were male and 1920 were female respectively.

All participants were aged from 6 to 16 years and patients with age > 18 years, having any systemic pathology or any associated syndrome, non-compliance patient and if any previous ocular surgery was performed were excluded in this study.

The study was approved by AMC MET medical college committee, Ahmedabad and was conducted under the guidance of Porecha Eye Hospital Committee. Formal written consent was obtained from the principal of the respective school on the behalf of the parents of the student studying in that particular school.

The detailed eye examination was performed by the senior optometrist and the other optometrist students of third year and interns which includes detailed history, visual acuity, colour vision assessment, refractive error measurement, ocular deviation determination, accommodation and convergence and lastly anterior and posterior segments evaluation.

Visual acuity and colour vision testing

We used the Snellen E, English and Gujarati chart for visual acuity (V/A) examination and the Ishihara colour test was used for red-green colour vision deficiency (CVD) screening.

The Snellen chart was hanging on the wall by measuring the distance of 6 meter with the help of measuring scale. The V/A was taken monocular and then binocular. If the child had glasses, then V/A was assessed with his/her own correction. If V/A was less than 20/40, then the measurement was repeated with pinhole and patient was then examined for the refractive error correction.

The Ishihara test consists of 38 plates were used for the assessment and the children were asked to read the colored number at the middle of each plate monocularly. If the child has the correction, the he/she reads with his /her own correction. The same procedure was repeated for the other eye but the order of presentation of the plates was changed to prevent cheating. If the child was able to read 34 or more correctly, then the child was considered as normal color vision, otherwise he/she was considered to be colour vision deficient.

Refractive errors

The refractive status of all children was measured by using the Autorefractometer (AR) by Nidek Company, the three readings were taken and then the average of all three readings was used as reference. Secondly, the optometrist performed the static retinoscopy with no cycloplegia but by fogging the eye to relax the accommodation. Lastly, by taking the reference of AR and retinoscopy, the subjective refraction was performed in the compliance patient. In the non-compliance patient, the retinoscopy was considered as final results. Depending upon the results, then patient was classified into myopia, hyperopia, astigmatism and anisometropia. Anisometropia was defined as spherical equivalent (SE) difference of at least one dioptre between the fellow eyes.

Ocular deviation

Ocular deviation was checked by using the cover test and all types of cover test i.e. Direct cover test, cover-uncover test and alternate cover test was performed to detect the phoria (latent squint) and tropia (manifest squint). For phoria measurement, the Maddox rod test was used and for tropia the Krimsky test was performed at 33cm for near and 6-meter distance for far. In order to reveal any Extraocular muscle dysfunction, the Broad H test was used to evaluate the muscles in nine different gazes.

Accommodation and Convergence

To evaluate any accommodation and convergence anomalies, the Near point of accommodation (NPA) and Near point of convergence (NPC) were measured by using the RAF ruler. The three

readings of each were taken and then average was recorded. Depending upon the results, they were classified as normal, insufficiency and excess.

Ocular structure

The ocular media was assessed by using the red reflex test with the help of direct ophthalmoscope. If any media opacities were detected, then the patient was referred at the higher center for the further evaluation and management.

Statistical analysis

To present data, we used mean value, standard deviation, median, range and percentage data. To evaluate the association of different factors with CVD, regression analysis was used. All statistical analysis were performed by using analysis tool inbuilt in excel software. P values less than 0.05 were considered as statistically significant.

Results

A total of 4057 children aged 6 to 16 years (mean, 12.23 ± 0.55) years were studied. Details of baseline demographics and ocular findings are shown in the Table 1. Color vision deficiency is detected in 20 children indicating a prevalence of 0.5%. The prevalence of CVD in male children was higher compared to female children.

Table 1 shows the mean age of patient with CVD and without CVD was 12.23 and 12.6 whose p-value was 1.28 which indicates no significant difference in the age group of both the category.

Figure 3 shows that out of 20 CVD patient, 60% were male and 40% were female students respectively and also the p-value was 0.17 which indicates that there was no clinically significant difference in the CVD ratio found in male and female student.

Figure 1 shows the mean V/A LogMAR of the children with CVD is normal compared to the children without CVD. Figure 2 shows that there is no correlation of children of CVD with refractive error, amblyopia, strabismus and anisometropia and the data are mentioned in the table.

Table 1 Demographic and ocular characteristics of children with normal and colour vision deficient.

FACTORS	TOTAL	COLOUR VISION DEFICIENCY(CVD)		P-VALUE
		NO	YES	
AGE (YEARS)				1.28
MEAN \pm SD	12.23 \pm 0.55	12.23 \pm 0.55	12.6 \pm 0.7	
MEDIAN (RANGE)	13(6-16)	13(6-16)	13.5(6-16)	
SEX				0.17
MALE	2137	2125	12	
FEMALE	1920	1912	8	
VISUAL ACUITY				0
MEAN \pm SD	0.004 \pm 0.016	0.004 \pm 0.016	0	
MEDIAN (RANGE)	0	0	0	
AMBLYOPIA				0
YES	12	20	0	
NO	4045	4037	0	0
REFRACTIVE ERROR				
YES	430	424	0	

NO	3627	3633	0	
ANISOMETROPIA(SE DIFFERENCE ≥1.0D)				0
YES	25	25	0	
NO	4032	4032	0	
STRABISMUS				0
YES(INCLUDING PHORIA AND TROPIA)	37	36	0	
NO	4020	4021	0	

Figure 1 Mean visual acuity (LogMAR) in children with and without colour vision deficiency (CVD). V/A, visual acuity; LogMAR, logarithm of the minimum angle of resolution.

Figure 2 Association of amblyopia, refractive error, strabismus and anisometropia in children with and without colour vision deficiency (CVD).

Figure 3 Percentage of Gender wise distribution of colour vision deficient children

Discussion

Considering this, the study was conducted to determine the prevalence rate of colour blindness in total 4057 students (2137 boys and 1920 girls) and also their relationship with refractive error, amblyopia, anisometropia and strabismus, in the age group between 6-16 years of age from different school of Ahmedabad, Bhuj, Surendranagar and Modasa by using Ishihara tests for color blindness, 38 plate edition. The Ishihara test showed good retest reliability. For other measurements, the standardized procedure such as retinoscopy, subjective refraction and cover test was performed.

On assessment, total 20 students (i.e. 0.5%) were found to be color blind which include 12 boys (0.6%) and 8 girls (0.4%). These 12 boys with colour blindness include 10 boys with deuteranomaly (0.47%) and 2 boys with protanomaly (0.09%). Another 8 girls with colour blindness include 5 girls with deuteranomaly (0.26%) and 3 girls with protanomaly (0.15%). From this study, it is observed that the prevalence of colour blindness in girls is 0.4%, which is similar to the prevalence of colour blindness observed in other studies i.e. 0.5%^[5], 0.4%^[6] and 0.38%^[7]. It is also observed that the prevalence of colour blindness in boys is 0.6% by this study which is significantly lesser than 3.16% rate observed in study done in Pune and Bhopal^[8] and also less than the lowest rate i.e. 2% observed in North America, Fiji and in certain Asian Indian tribes^[9]. Thus though the prevalence rate is different in boys compared to girls in the previous literature but a difference in the prevalence rate is observed which may be attributed to the different community or geographical or genetic variation of the different population. But study can be done with more sample size and categorizing in different districts of Gujarat state.

Along with prevalence rate, the study also shows that the children with CVD have no relation with amblyopia, refractive error (all patients were emmetropic), strabismus and anisometropia. Which is slightly different from the study^[10] which indicates that CVD was correlated with lower VA and amblyopia, there was no relationship between CVD and type of amblyopia, refractive error, anisometropia or strabismus.

CONCLUSION

In our study we concluded that the colour blindness mostly affects boys but it can affect both the gender. Red and green deficiency is most common because of its genetic inheritance. Along with it, there was no relationship between CVD and type of amblyopia, refractive error,

anisometropia or strabismus. So, early detection of colour vision abnormalities allows parents, teachers and guardians to make adjustments in children teaching methods and can also guide them for the various career opportunities that they select for their future because certain professions require normal colour vision such as traffic policeman, navy, railways and other certain jobs.

Thus, school screening programs should be conducted and includes colour vision test in the examination which would help in early detection and along with its other ocular anomalies can be detected which can be treated at an early stage which can prevent children to become amblyopic or low vision.

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